

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: YOWIKA****FIRST NAME: KAMENE****PROGRAM CODE: DTCD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author () did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2017 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your R.P.)(samples below):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019,1- 4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019,5-13)
3. How to Cite (EUCLID 2019, 6)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
5. Paraphrase (EUCLID 2019, 8-10)
6. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
7. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2019, 56- 61)

IMPROVE YOUR ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As I was born and raised in a country where English is the primary language, I have always been fluent in English. Nevertheless, as I have dyslexia, my writing skills have not always been the best. Upon finishing my degree in England, I assumed that EUCLID's writing standard would not be too difficult to grasp. I was pleased to find my assumption to be correct. The teachings in EUCLID'S course materials match the instructions of many U.K. Authors. Such as *Helen, Sword*, and *James, Hartley*. Although I have previously learned academic writing throughout my academic years, I quickly realised there was so much more to know when reading the ACA-401D coursepack and after watching the 14min introduction video. As *Jidda Krishnamurti* reminds us, "There is no end to education" (Krishnamurti 2013). The materials provided in this coursepack have taught me how to present an idea, develop a thesis, and adequately research topics to create appropriate academic writing. To answer the task at hand, in the future of my EUCLID studies and my daily/work-life after EUCLID.

2) PLAN YOUR ESSAY

The first chapter of the ACA-401D Period 1 coursepack presents the different stages of academic writing. Notably, there is no universally agreed-upon definition of the phrase ‘essay’. However, numerous authors have given several meanings. Cuddon explained that an essay ‘discusses, either formally or informally, the topic/topics present’ (Cuddon 2013). Upon further research, I discovered that Michel de Montaigne, a French author, coined the term ‘essay’ (Nordquist 2019). Hogue describes academic writing as a “process that has several steps”, rather than a one-step action (Oshima and Hogue 2006, 2). I agree with this perspective, meaning I am willing to regard academic essays as a linear process. The coursepack has supported this idea as the materials suggest a clear structure for academic papers is needed to present your thoughts on the question at hand. First, we must begin with an introduction; secondly, we must go on to the main body, and finally, we must provide a conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 3). An understandable order on my various thoughts will make my paper much more painless for the instructor to follow. To present my ideas coherently, before beginning to write my essay, I must first create a well-defined essay plan.

Throughout my academic years, I had misunderstood the importance of organising my ideas. Instead, I had often found myself writing an essay without planning what I would include and its organisational structure. While several students are attracted to the concept of freely brainstorming their essay. This method almost always leaves the student with an incoherent and disorganised academic writing. Our course pack states that writing an essay plan “will help you work out how to answer the question and how to structure the essay” (EUCLID 2019, 2). I concur with this statement, as by having a well-defined structure, the student’s ideas are made clear to the marker. By developing a preliminary essay plan, which includes the essay’s research and structure, the students are provided with a guide on how they will present their thoughts and ideas (EUCLID 2019, 1). I found it great the coursepack mentions this because when initially creating your essay plan, you need to research the topic. By planning the evidence, examples, and structure of your essay, the coursepack indirectly insists that you will be better positioned to present an organised and well-structured paper (EUCLID 2019, 3). This is because planning will help you convey your ideas to the reader more effectively, as it will take less effort for the reader to follow an organised paper.

It is common practice for universities to emphasise the importance of planning your essay. Not only is planning important for academics, but it also has essential for many other fields. For example, a scientist will need to prepare before carrying out research. Even in the aspect of businesses, planning is necessary. A business plan provides a coherent idea of the company and “its external environment” (Berry 2009). Markedly, planning has also impacted the work of several theorists (Friedmann 2008). I have written several papers, such as; research papers, short stories, descriptive and analytical essays and various seminar papers. Before writing these papers, I would have to plan the organisation of the ideas I wish to present and how the essay will be structure. When I failed to do so, it was always noticed and pointed out by the marker. Therefore I

fully agree with the coursepack instructions to organise our ideas by creating an essay plan (EUCLID 2019, 2).

I was pleased that the course materials provide several points necessary for creating an essay plan. Firstly we must research and come up with several answers to the question or task at hand. When you've picked the most substantial arguments, you then decide on the order you wish to present these arguments(EUCLID 2019, 2). By planning the essay's ideas and structure, the writer can freely and appropriately express his or her opinions, ensuring that the academic paper works coherently.

3) PLAGIARISM

In chapter 2 of the coursepack, Dr Kabiru Gulma and Prof. Laurent Cleenwerck explained plagiarism. The materials go on to state that “plagiarism occurs when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5). Julia Ryan, a lecturer at George Washington University, discovered that 7 out of 42 students plagiarised most of their papers (Lathrop and Foss 2000). In contrast, a study comprised of McCabe and Trevion found that 84% of students have admitted to plagiarising at least once. These different findings and many others suggest that the amount of times students plagiarise is unclear. Gerald Nelms supports this theory. Nelms explains that ‘the fact is, we do not know exactly how much students plagiarise’ (Nelms 2012).

Throughout my academic years, all the institutions I attended made it clear that I could not copy and paste another person's work, without giving them credit. Therefore it was not a surprise to me when the coursepack mentioned that plagiarism “is a serious offence that could have serious consequences” (EUCLID 2019, 3,5). I agree with the coursepack labelling, stealing another person's work as “wrong and unethical” primarily because plagiarism can be classified as a type of theft, which the writer then benefits from. Although plagiarism is not a crime, it can be seen as a copyright infringement. Notably, plagiarism comes from “Plagiarie” a Latin word for a kidnapper. (Dhammi and Ul Haq 2016) I liked that the coursepack suggested ways to avoid plagiarism; Citation, quotations and paraphrase (EUCLID 2019, 6,7,8). I also appreciated that plagiarism was addressed very early in the course, ensuring no room for confusion among EUCLID students on EUCLID's regulations on submitting someone else's work. It serves as a warning to potential plagiarists and provides us with ways to easily avoid plagiarism.

4) STYLE GUIDE

Lindy Woodrow, a senior lecturer at the University of Sydney Australia, points out that there are guidelines to follow when writing an academic paper, which the specific academic department will usually publish (Woodrow 2014, 170). Woodrow explained that the three primary style guides in academic writing are; APA (American Psychological Association), MLA (Modern Language Association), and Chicago style.

Chapter 5 of the study pack recommended that students should follow the Chicago style. However, it also mentions that other international style guides will also be accepted (EUCLID 2019, 24).

I was never introduced to the concept of style guides until I began my course at EUCLID. I previously believed that the style guide only related to the style of the referencing. However, the coursepack cleared misunderstanding by giving me clarity on the matter. I'm now aware that the style guides refer to 'the basic rules of writing, which allow you to ensure that the written style employed is consistent' (EUCLID 2019, 24). When writing research papers or any other academic papers, I never took note of the style guide needed, neither did I view it as necessary. I was pleased to see that the coursepack pointed out the different aspects of a style guide, from grammar to font usage (EUCLID 2019, 25). Although it may not be a complete list, it still gave me an idea of what to look for when applying a particular style guide. This allowed me to consider what style guide I would like to choose when writing an academic essay.

I agree with the coursepack that following a style guide ensures that the writer's personal style does not affect academic writing. Additionally, a style guide is essential in building an academic paper that is 'coherent and consistent' (EUCLID 2019, 24). It was also significant to see that style guides must also be considered in our daily lives/work (EUCLID 2019, 25). As it will provide us with practice on how to follow a specific style, which complies with that the reader wants. Furthermore, I liked that the materials provided examples of several style guides and how to access them. E.g., The economist style guide and the BBC new style guide (EUCLID 2019, 25). Both these style guides are very different. The Economist style guide is the writing manual of the economist newspaper. In contrast, the BBC style guide relates to grammar, spelling and punctuation for the BBC journalist and most news organisations in the U.K. By giving us these various style guides; I believe the materials teach us to distinguish style guides that best fit the task. Either for future academic writing or in my work life in the future.

5) AMERICAN ENGLISH VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Chapter 6 of the coursepack introduces us to the fundamental differences between 'American English and British English'. The materials explain that SAE (American English) and SBE (British English) are more similar than they are different. However, it mentions that American English is the primary influence of the 'worlds English' (EUCLID 2019, 27). While researching, I discovered that there are several types of world Englishes' (Jenkins 2009). For example, there is Canadian English, Austrian English, India English, Nigerian English, etc. However, the reading materials only covered the differences between British and American English, as they are the only two Englishes necessary for completing a degree at EUCLID. The differences between the two can be found in the dates, vocabulary, spelling, grammar and punctuation (EUCLID 2019, 27-35). I support Tottie belief that the grammatic differences are more extensive than the difference in pronunciations, spelling and vocab' (Tottie 2002, 10).

While studying in Switzerland, England, Nigeria and America, English was continuously emphasised as an essential and beneficial tool for an individual throughout my academic years. As we live in an English dominated world, speaking English opens up a person to numerous opportunities. Although my country has over 525 languages, English is its first language. Upon discovering, while watching the introduction video and the materials provided, that students could choose either to write in American English or British English, I was quite pleased and surprised. I was pleased because I just finished my masters and undergrad at a British English University. Thus, I would not be required to change too much to adapt to EUCLID regulations. Nevertheless, I was still surprised, as at my previous schools and university, we were thought to adhere to one English style.

I appreciate how the coursebook provides numerous examples of the differences and similarities of SAE and SBE (EUCLID 2019, 27-35). I was happy that the materials taught both American and British English because I was unaware of the complexity surrounding the differences between the two. Before reading the materials, I had also overlooked several similarities between the two. For example, while some words' spelling is different, the pronunciations are the same: cheque and check, tyre and tire, ax and axe and so forth (EUCLID 2019, 28). The various examples in British and American English grammar differences were useful to see (EUCLID 2019, 29). Rather than just explaining the differences, the coursepack showed me how to apply these differences in academic style writing, depending on what English I choose to write in. It also allows me to see both English styles, giving me a chance to decide what English suits me better.

Nevertheless, I do wish there were some explanation, rather than 90% examples. It would have given me more clarity on what to look for when spotting the similarities and differences between SAE and SBE. Despite this, the coursepack was very good at covering the wide ranges of differences and similarities between the two types of Englishes. Among the differences mentioned in the coursepack, I remember struggling the most throughout my academic years with the spelling differences. The spelling differences between SAE and SBE have been described as a "conscious decision" by educators, editors and politicians (Gelderen 2006). This can be seen in the coursebook where math is spelt maths, and polyethene is spelt polythene (EUCLID 2019, 28). These difference illustrate the differences in spelling as usually small. In my academic life and daily life, I had often mixed up American spelling with British spelling. For instance, I would write denfense rather than defence. The latter was correct, rather than the former as I was at a British university. Similarly, I would write analyze instead of analyse. Thanks to my lectures' various corrections and the coursepack, I can now distinguished British English spelling from American English.

6) LATIN, THE DEA LANGUAGE

Despite not studying Latin throughout my academic years, I have always recognised the importance of Latin. I typically used Latin abbreviations in my daily life, when writing an email to a lecturer or in my academic papers. Abbreviations such as IBID and, e.g. I had previously used these abbreviations unaware it was Latin. I believe it is accurate to consider Latin a 'dead language'. Although Latin plays a significant role in

western societies (such as in the catholic church), it no longer has native speakers. However, Latin should not be referred to as an extinct language, because despite it no longer having native speakers, it is still frequently used. The death of Latin is not straight forward, as Latin is still widely used, for example, the pope tweets in Latin and the English language still uses Latin abbreviations. Latin has just merely changed (Roberts 2020).

Numerous Latin abbreviations are still commonly used every day. For example to show it is morning 'am' is used and say its afternoon 'pm' is used. These two abbreviations distinguish time frames across the world. Even though these symbols are used every day, it is unlikely people know these symbols are Latin and what they mean. AM stands for 'Ante Meridiem', while PM stands for 'Post Meridiem' (EUCLID 2019, 56-57). Another aspect of our lives where Latin abbreviations are commonly used is in academic writing. For example, i.e. (id est), which means 'that is', etc (et cetera) which stands for 'and so on' (EUCLID 2019, 57), are widely used in academic papers. I.E. may be necessary in academic writing when trying to explain or give an example of a specific topic. While etc may be used when there are too many examples to list out. Another Latin abbreviation common in academic writing is et al. (et alii) which means 'and other people' (EUCLID 2019, 57). This symbol can be used in footnotes when the writer wishes to demonstrate there are several more authors. Latin abbreviations may also be used when constructing an email, for example, N.B (Nota bene) alerts the reader to note a particular thing carefully or well (EUCLID 2019, 57).

When studying law, I also noticed that Latin expressions were also frequently used. V. (versus) is used to name the two parties in the case (the claimant against the defendant) (EUCLID 2019, 58). While bone fide can be found under the law of trust, which illustrates that the beneficiary or trustee must enter into the contract in good faith, therefore, free from fraud or deceit. (EUCLID 2019, 59). Quid Pro Quo (means giving one valuable thing for another) is found under contract law, which means a contract can not be enforced unless there is mutual consideration between both parties (EUCLID 2019, 60).

Out of the Latin abbreviations and expression provided in the coursebook, I noticed that I frequently used P.S (post scriptum) the most, which stands for 'after writing' throughout my academic years and daily life (EUCLID 2019, 58). Whether when writing emails or text messages, to convey to the reader, there was more to add. Although I had seen e.g. (exempli gratia) and V.V (vice versa) earlier in life (EUCLID 2019, 56-57), it was only recently I discovered the meaning of these two expressions. E.g. means 'for example', while vice versa stands for 'the other way round.'

7) CONCLUSION

This period was the first step in completing my PHD in counter-terrorism and deradicalisation. It was entertaining to read the ACA-401D period (1) coursepack and the student orientation handout. As well as watch the video presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck.

Period one examined my basic English knowledge and provided me with additional comprehension on matters I was previously unaware of. This coursepack gave me a strong foundation on how to compose my academic writing moving forward. In the future of my studies, I will plan my essays or tasks ahead, rather than freely writing them. I will make sure I take precaution to avoid plagiarism by adequately quoting and paraphrasing authors. I will also ensure I pay more attention to the English I choose to employ when writing my papers. Additionally, I will practice how to follow the Chicago style guide. Although Latin can be considered a dead language as it no longer has native speakers, it still has an enormous impact on the English language.

Therefore it is clear the teaching in ACA-401D period one (1) would help me in my studies at EUCLID.

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